

THE EFFECT OF LITERACY INSTRUCTION ON ENGLISH LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT IN PRIVATE PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN RWANDA: A CASE OF BUGESERA DISTRICT

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Abstract: This study investigated the effect of literacy instruction on English language development in PRIVATE primary schools in Bugesera, Rwanda. Specifically, this study identified the literacy instruction that affect English language development in PRIVATE primary schools in Bugesera District, evaluated the level of English development level that is due to use of literacy instruction in PRIVATE primary schools of Bugesera District, Rwanda and determined the effect of use of literacy instruction on English language development in PRIVATE primary schools in Bugesera, Rwanda. The sample size was sample size is 33 respondents, 51 Parents of children with a sample size of 34 respondents. Primary source was gathered using questionnaire, interviews and observation methods to triangulate data. Simple random and purposive sampling techniques were parents, English teachers and Head teachers. Qualitative data were collected using interview guide while quantitative data was obtained using questionnaire. The study analyzed data using both qualitative and quantitative techniques. Content analysis helped qualitative data analysis and quantitative data was presented using statistical package for social sciences by descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (correlational and regression analysis). Regarding the first objective, the study reveals that literacy instruction. Writing literacy education, listening literacy, speaking literacy skills, and reading literacy teaching have the most significant effects, with 61.2% strongly agreeing and 71.6% agreeing. To the second objective, results 91.6% show a strongly agreed that The capacity to comprehend English language demonstrates the level of English development. Moreover, 82.4% accepted that The ability to express thoughts in English indicates the level of English development, 91.2% strongly agree that The capacity to follow a talk in English demonstrates one's degree of English development. The third objective felt Results on correlation between use of English instruction and English language development in PRIVATE primary schools in Bugesera indicated that most measures were positively associated with each other. Since the degree of significance was less than 0.05. It was proposed that the Ministry of education should provide enough funds to improve English proficiency deemed to enhance the level of English development, undertake trainings, seminar and capacity development program to encourage knowledge and improving English proficiency factors the level of understanding English. Head teachers shall monitor teachers for being sure that effectiveness for English instruction. Teachers should try to produce direct support The study recommends future researches to carry out studies in the following subject: The effect of creating awareness on importance of English language among students at all levels of education

Keywords: Academic Performance, English language, Instruction, Language, Literacy, Literacy Instruction.

1. INTRODUCTION TO THE STUDY

Background of the Study

English, one of the most widely spoken languages on the entire globe, is the native language of five countries (Australia, Canada, England, New Zealand, and the United Kingdom). According to Kachru (2018), this is the "inner circle" of the United States of America. It is also used as an official language in a number of other countries where it has been introduced (Roy-Campbell, 2015). These nations include former British colonies in Africa and Asia.

All around the world, English has become only one of hundreds of languages spoken in India throughout the years. According to the People's Linguistic Survey of marser (2016), India has 780 live languages and maybe 100 unreported languages, however Ethnologue (2019) has 447 alive languages (both sources are cited in Bedi, 2020). Graddol (2016) estimates that between 55 and 350 million Indians speak English, whereas the 2011 India census revealed that 260,000 individuals regard English as their first language, 83 million as their second language, and 46 million as their third. However, reliable contemporary numbers on the number of English speakers in the nation are lacking (Nath, 2020). Data on competence is similarly scarce; however, according to the EF's English competence index, India ranks 48th out of 112 nations with an overall proficiency grade of "moderate" (Education First, 2021). However, the country's linguistic variety is so rich and diverse that, according to Agnihotri (2007, 2014) (quoted in Heugh et al., 2019:18), "people have multilingual rather than one specific language." medium schools in contrast to schools in the country that use other languages as a medium of instruction. According to data from the 2019 National Statistical Survey published in the press (The Indian Express, 2020), the proportion of English-medium students in lower private primary (Grades 1 to 5) increased to 23.2 percent in 2017-18 from 22.3 percent in 2014, while it increased to 21 percent from 19.3 percent in upper Private primary. Except for Karnataka, English was determined to be the most favored language of instruction in the southern states of India, according to a recent poll done by the Unified District Information System in 2019 and reported in The Federal 2021.

The study ought to investigate the effect of literacy instruction on English language development in private primary schools in Bugesera, Rwanda.

Problem Statement

English, along with Kinyarwanda and French, is one of Rwanda's three official languages (Sibomana, 2018). English is taught in schools from kindergarten to university, and it is employed as a medium of teaching starting in fourth grade. The Literacy and English Framework, according to Cochran (2016), emphasizes the development of critical and creative thinking, as well as fluency in hearing and speaking, reading, and writing, as well as the personal, interpersonal, and team-working skills required in life and the workplace. The framework has detailed descriptions. English is a required subject in Rwandan schools, preparing pupils for future employment in communication and technology. However, according to Rwanda's 4th Population and Housing Census (NISR, 2014), just 7% of the population can read and write English, and pupils' performance continues to deteriorate. As Amuthelezi (2016) points out, poor English performance is a worldwide problem. Kagwesage (2013) observed in her thesis that even students in higher education institutions were not prepared to follow their English courses.

Since English became the language of instruction, no research has been conducted to investigate the effect of literacy instruction on English language development in Private primary schools in Rwanda. Therefore, the present study was intending to investigate the effect of literacy instruction on English language development in Private primary schools in Bugesera, Rwanda.

Objectives of the Study

General objective of the Study

The general objective of this study was to investigate the effect of literacy instruction on English language development in Private primary schools in Bugesera, Rwanda.

Specific Objectives

- i. To identify the literacy instruction that affect English language development in private primary schools in Bugesera District.
- ii. To evaluate the level of English development level that is due to use of literacy instruction in Private primary schools of Bugesera District, Rwanda.
- iii. To determine the effect of use of literacy instruction on English language development in private primary schools in Bugesera, Rwanda.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Theoretical Literature

This section discusses the several kinds of literature that have been highlighted as far as the The current topic will be a concern.

2.1.1 Literacy skills across languages and possibilities for transfer

Transferring from a native language to English is dependent on the similarities between the two languages. Learning to read English entails matching discrete visual symbols to spoken linguistic units of sound (Ziegler and Goswami, 2012). Language learners may be familiar with writing systems that differ in their degree of resemblance to English ; for example, a native Spanish speaker may be familiar with an alphabetic system comparable to that of English, but a native Chinese speaker will be familiar with a nonalphabetic system. Moreover, some languages do not have a written form. Languages that do have a writing system portray their oral languages in a variety of ways, both in terms of symbols and phonological units represented in type. Nonalphabetic languages, such as Japanese Kanji and Chinese, convey morphological and phonological information rather than just phonological information. Some languages, such as Korean, Russian, and Hebrew, have alphabetic writing systems but employ non-Latin scripts. Even alphabetic languages that utilize the Latin script (e.g., Malay, Turkish, and Welsh) can be substantially distinct from English (Kumar, 2023).

2.1.2 Access to Language and Literacy Practice outside Classrooms

Adult language learners can engage in ongoing exchanges in both spoken and written English outside of the classroom (Reder, 2014). Successful language acquisition necessitates considerable second language input as well as opportunities to connect with people and express one's own ideas, thoughts, and opinions through language (Ellis, 2016). Exposure to rich language patterns is also beneficial since learners are very sensitive and easily detect frequent patterns in a language (Vouloumanos, 2008). As a result, it is critical not to isolate language learners from native speakers and to increase exposure to the second language through a variety of settings.

Technology, such as Internet sites, remote learning, and email, is a potential method for providing practice outside of the classroom. Although some new study has been conducted with adult language learners, the majority of studies on the usefulness of technology with this demographic is outdated and unclear (Abraham, 2008; Torgerson, Porthouse, and Brooks, 2003). Because the practicality, usability, and efficacy of self-access models via technology for adult language learners have not been thoroughly investigated, a new generation of research is required (DUSSLING, 2023).

2.1.3. Reading and writing literacy instruction

Reading and Writing in the Early Class Anderson (Dhieni, 2018) reveals that the preliminary reading is an integrated reading activity, emphasizing the introduction of letters and words and relating them to sounds. According to Zuchdi and Budiasih (1996: 50) preliminary reading given gradually, namely pre-reading and reading. At the pre-reading stage, students are taught and familiarized to do the following activities: (1) A good sitting posture at the time of reading, (2) How to place a book on a desk, (3) How to hold a book, (3) How to open and turn pages, and (4) View and pay attention to writing. The preliminary writing ability is not much different from the preliminary reading ability. At a basic level, learning to write is more oriented towards non-mechanical abilities. Students are trained to be able to write (similar to the ability to paint or draw) written symbols when coupled in a structure, the symbols become meaningful. Furthermore, with this basic skill, students are gradually led to the ability to pour ideas, thoughts, feelings, into the form of written language through the written symbols they have mastered. This is the true writing ability. Students must understand that the writing has meaning and represents spoken language. Writing is a medium for expressing ideas, feelings, and conveying messages.

2.1.4. Affective Aspects of Learning and Instruction

Field research indicates the importance of attending to the affective aspects of instruction (Wrigley, 2015), although more systematic research on English language learners' affective responses to literacy instruction is needed to develop motivating and supportive approaches. Field observations show that beginning learners are reluctant to use English inside and outside the classroom because they may feel insecure about their linguistic skills. English learners can become demotivated and frustrated with the slow pace of literacy instruction, repetitive instruction (e.g., as teachers try to catch up students who have missed a class), and a focus on topics that are not well matched to the learner's education level, interests, or familiarity with U.S. culture (e.g., a focus on holidays when content related to science and technology and topical discussions are preferred).

Literacy skills

Literacy can be comprehended as the skill of understanding the alphabets, lettering, and also the ability to read and write. Literacy is the ability of one's language (listening, speaking, reading, and writing) to communicate in different ways according to its purpose. Sulzby (2016) defines literacy specifically, that literacy as the ability to read and write. This is due to the opinions of Grabe & Kaplan (2011) and Graff (2016) who interpreted literacy as the ability to read and write. Literacy is very essential for students because the skill in literacy has a significant influence to the students succeed in learning and their daily life.

Empirical Review

According to The author investigates the present level of knowledge and hypotheses on the issue, as well as the topic's historical background, in the empirical review phase of the literature review.

The literacy instruction that affect English language development in Private primary schools

According to a research done in the United States by (Snyder, 2019), the expanding English language learner (ELL) population demands an investigation of reading intervention efficacy with this demographic. Because of the significance of reading skills and the natural linguistic challenges that ELLs face, reading success is of special concern. This article examines existing evidence on the effectiveness of reading interventions with ELLs published between January 2003 and July 2015. Studies with significant effect sizes that incorporated phonics, phonemic awareness, fluency, comprehension, and/or vocabulary as intervention components and outcome measurements were specifically examined. The findings show that comprehensive treatments for phonemic awareness, phonics, fluency, and comprehension are successful, as is vocabulary education for improving vocabulary results

The level of English development level that is due to use of literacy instruction in PRIVATE primary schools

(Teng, 2019) carried out a small-scale investigation of the results of teaching metacognitive reading strategies to English language learners at a Hong Kong international school. In this study, 25 Private primary school pupils (Grade 5) who are learning English as a second language took part. Ten process-based reading lessons included metacognitive teaching. Data were gathered from the reading notes that students made, the post-reading reflection reports, the group conversations that teachers supervised, and two different types of reading exams. Results showed that the young students could describe a number of knowledge-related influences on their reading. A greater awareness of the role that metacognitive information plays in enhancing reading comprehension, a deeper grasp of the nature and demands of reading, and an improvement in confidence while managing reading activities were also noted by students. Additionally, the student's reading abilities improved in comparison to those of those in a control group who received no metacognitive training. This study emphasizes how metacognitive teaching might improve the reading literacy of English language learners in Private primary schools.

The effect of use of literacy instruction on English language development in Private primary schools

Chinese researchers (Teng L. S., 2020) performed a study to examine how an SRL strategy-based writing intervention affected students' L2 writing competency, reported usage of SRL techniques, and academic self-efficacy. 80 undergraduate students who were enrolled in a Chinese university's academic writing course provided the data. The control group took an academic writing course for the same amount of time as the intervention group's five-month SRL strategy-based training on how to use various SRL strategies' aspects.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 2.1 Conceptual framework

Source: Researcher (2023)

The conceptual framework will be a summary of the relationship between the variables in this study. The figure above shows several factors that English language Development. Writing literacy instruction, reading literacy instruction, Listening literacy instruction, Speaking literacy instruction. The dependent variables are : The student understands the meaning in English. The ability to grasp English language, The capacity to convey thoughts in English and The ability to follow discussion in English is indicated in the above figure.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design

According to McCombes (2019), the research design refers to the overall strategy that is chosen to integrate the different components of the study in a coherent and logical way, thereby ensuring the effective address of the research problem; it constitutes the blueprint for the collection, measurement, and analysis of data. It is a framework that includes methods and procedures for data gathering, analysis, and interpretation. This study employed a descriptive survey research design and included both quantitative and qualitative approaches. On the one hand, a survey was used with the quantitative technique, in which questionnaires were sent to teachers and sampled students over the course of the study.

Target population

A research population is a large group of people or things that are the subject of a scientific inquiry. Research is carried out for the benefit of the general Private (Hassan, 2019). The population in this study consisted of 100 English teachers with a sample size of 67 respondents, 50 heads of teachers, whose sample size was 33 respondents, and 51 parents of children with a sample size of 34 respondents. Through this, the total population were 201 respondents, with a total sample of 134 respondents from 32 secondary schools in three Bugesera District sectors, such as Gashora, Kamabuye, and Nyarugenge.

Sample design

The technique used to select the sample population is called sampling design, and it enables the researcher to generalize the findings to the complete group targeted in the study (Cochran, 2016).

Sample size determination

Sample size is described by Kothari (2008) as "the variety of devices to be chosen from the universe to constitute a sample." Without having to learn about the entire population, one can learn about it by studying a sample of it. The sample size of the study was calculated using Slovin's formula. Slovin's Formula provides the sample size (n), the use of the identified population size (N), and the perfect error or the level of self-confidence (e). Put the N and e values into the formula.

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where n: sample

N: population

(e): sampling error = 0.05

$$\text{The sample size: } n = \frac{201}{1+201(0.05)^2} = 134$$

Table 3.1: The distribution of the sample size

Category	Target Population	Sample size
Head Teachers	50	33
English Teachers	100	67
Parents	51	34
Total:	201	134

Source: Researcher (2023)

Table 3. 1 The distribution of the sample size

The Private primary method of gathering data from respondents was chosen to reflect the study's complete population and will be an improved structured questionnaire, according to the researcher. In addition to using questionnaire data, the researcher conducted guided interviews with head teachers.

Sampling Technique

Purposive sampling, according to Nikolopoulou (2022), refers to a class of non-probability sampling procedures in which units are chosen based on features that you require in your sample. A simple random sample is a randomly selected subset of a population. In this sampling method, each member of the population has an exactly equal chance of being selected. Thomas (2020). This study used purposive sampling techniques to choose English teachers from three sectors in Bugesera district and also used simple random sampling to choose the parents and head teachers as respondents. These techniques were used by the researcher based on the experience, qualities, and knowledge of all respondents to provide virtue information.

Data Collection Methods

Data collection is a systematic procedure for compiling measurements or observations. Data gathering enables you to get first-hand information and unique insights into your study challenge, whether you are conducting research for corporate, governmental, or academic objectives. This study employed data-gathering methods, including questionnaires and documentation. Research procedures that used in data analysis are discussed.

Data Collection Instruments

According to Galton (2021), a questionnaire is a research tool made up of a list of questions (items) designed to record respondents' replies in a consistent way. In this study, the questionnaire included a series of open questions that helped the researcher get the needed information from the respondents, and the questionnaire was distributed to the respondents for collecting qualitative data considering the set objectives of the study.

According to Paige (2012), documentation is a system that formally acknowledges the sources consulted for the research. According to Robert (2014), one of the basic advantages of document studies is the ability to explore the sources more fully in order to obtain additional information on an aspect of the subject. This is an extensive study and review of published documents, reports, magazines, journals, and policy reports related to the topic. This is important because it reviews the literature and tries to locate global perspectives in order to make a comparative framework for analysis and evaluation for readers; therefore, the researcher used this documentary technique in order to conduct research and get secondary data.

The researcher formulated an interview guide to obtain qualitative information. Therefore, an interview guide has been adopted owing to its ability to give the interviewee a chance to express his or her ideas freely and deeply and to ensure reliable and valid assessment of special systems or procedures.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS INTERPRETATIONS AND DISCUSSIONS**Presentation of Findings**

Findings are divided into three research specific objectives as follows: To identify the literacy instruction that affect English language development in Private primary schools in Bugesera District, to evaluate the level of English development level that is due to use of literacy instruction in PRIVATE primary schools of Bugesera District, Rwanda and To determine the effect of use of literacy instruction on English language development in Private primary schools in Bugesera, Rwanda.

The literacy instruction that affect English language development in Private primary schools in Bugesera District

For this study it had the first objective of identifying the literacy instruction that affect English language development in Private primary schools in Bugesera District. To achieve this objective, this study required participate to provide responses by filling the research tool. The researcher used a five Likert scape from strongly agree to strongly disagree.

Table 4.1: Teachers view on the literacy instruction that affect english language development in private primary schools in bugesera district

Statements	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly agree		Mean	Std
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Writing literacy education has the potential to influence English language development.	4	6.0	4	6.0	0	0.0	18	26.9	41	61.2	1.6	1.14
Reading literacy teaching has an influence on English language development.	4	6.0	8	11.9	0	0.0	7	10.4	48	71.6	1.7	1.29
Listening literacy teaching can have an Effect on English language development.	4	6.6	4	6.6	11	16.4	22	32.8	28	38.8	1.15	2.07
Speaking literacy skills has the ability to influence English language development.	8	11.9	4	1.1	0	0.0	14	20.9	41	61.2	1.4	0.7

Source: Primary Data (2023)

Findings from Table 4.1 demonstrates responses provided on the the literacy instruction that affect English language development in Private primary schools in Bugesera District. Therefore, 61.2% strongly agreed that Writing literacy education has the potential to influence English language development at mean response of 1.6 with a standard deviation equal to 1.14, 38.8% of participants accepted that Listening literacy teaching can have an Effect on English language development while 32.8% Agreed with the statement at mean response of 1.15 with a standard deviation equal to 2.07, 61.2% of respondents agreed that Speaking literacy skills has the ability to influence English language development at mean response of 1.4 with a standard deviation equal to 0.7, Finally, 71.6% of respondents agreed that Reading literacy teaching has an influence on English language development at mean response of 1.7 with a standard deviation equal to 1.27. results presented in this study did not contradict with observation of (Slavin, 2021) revealed The best-evidence synthesis review technique is used, which includes a systematic literature search, quantification of outcomes as effect sizes, and comprehensive discussion of individual studies that match inclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria were satisfied by 17 research in total. A weighted effect size of +0.33 was calculated, which is substantially different from zero (p.05). Although the number of high-quality research is minimal, the study suggests that available data favors bilingual techniques, particularly paired bilingual strategies that teach reading in the local language and English at separate times each day. However, further study utilizing longitudinal, randomized designs is required to establish how to best promote reading success for all.

The level of English development level that is due to use of literacy instruction in Private primary schools of Bugesera District

This section provides data on students' performance in national exams that is due to local language use. To achieve this objective, participants filed questionnaire; the researcher also analyzed different documents about primary school performance in English in lower primary schools. Respondent's opinions are rated using strongly disagree to strongly agree.

Table 4.2 English Teachers percprtions on The level of English development level that is due to use of literacy instruction in Private primary schools of Bugesera District

Statements	Storngly Disgree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly agree		Mean	Std
	N	%	N	%	N%	N	%	N	%			
The student understands the meaning in English	3	4.5	3	4.5	0	0.0	13	19.4	48	71.6	1.5	1.03
The capacity to comprehend English language.	3	4.5	6	9.0	0	0.0	4	6.0	54	80.6	1.5	1.15
The ability to express thoughts in English.	3	4.5	3	4.5	7	10.4	14	20.9	40	59.7	1.7	1.1
The capacity to follow a talk in English.	6	9.0	3	4.5	0	0.0	8	11.9	50	74.6	1.2	1.7
The degree of English development is indicated by learner marks in English text.	9	13.4	3	4.5	3	4.5	0	0.0	52	77.6	1.7	1.4

Source: Primary Data (2023)

Table 4.2 demonstrated that 71.6 of participants accepted the student understands the meaning in English, 80.6% show a strongly agreed that the capacity to comprehend English language. Moreover, 59.7% accepted that The ability to express thoughts in English, 74.6% strongly agree that the capacity to follow a talk in English and, 77.6% strongly agree that the degree of English development is indicated by learner marks in English text. (BUTLER, 2018) In response to the rising need to nurture conversational abilities in English, several Asian nations where English is taught as a foreign language have lately introduced English at the primary school level. However, the majority of primary school teachers in such nations may not be fully qualified to teach English; consequently, increasing their English proficiency and teaching abilities has become a problem.

Table 4.3 Parents perceptions on the level of academic performance in English

Statements	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly agree		Mean	Std
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
	The student understands the meaning in English shows the level of English development level	1	2.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	4	1.1	29		
The capacity to comprehend English language demonstrates the level of English development.	1	2.9	1	2.9	0	0.0	1	2.9	31	91.2	1.2	0.8
The ability to express thoughts in English indicates the level of English development.	1	2.9	1	2.9	1	2.9	3	8.8	28	82.4	1.3	0.9
The capacity to follow a talk in English demonstrates one's degree of English development.	1	2.9	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	5.9	31	91.2	1.4	1.17

Source: Primary Data (2023)

Table 4.3 demonstrated that 85.3 of participants accepted the the student understands the meaning in English shows the level of English development level, 91.6% show a strongly agreed that the capacity to comprehend English language demonstrates the level of English development. Moreover, 82.4% accepted that the ability to express thoughts in English indicates the level of English development, 91.2% strongly agree that the capacity to follow a talk in English demonstrates one's degree of English development.

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of the Findings

The literacy instruction that affect English language development in Private primary schools

This first objective of the study identified the literacy instruction that affect English language development in Private primary schools in Bugesera District. The statements are used in the real examination: "Writing literacy education has the potential to influence English language development, reading literacy teaching has an influence on English language development, listening literacy teaching can have an Effect on English language development and Speaking literacy skills has the ability to influence English language development.

The level of English development level that is due to use of literacy instruction in Private primary schools

This second objective of the study evaluated the level of English development that is due to the use of literacy instruction in private primary schools in Bugesera District: the student understands the meaning in English, has the capacity to comprehend the English language, has the ability to express thoughts in English, and has the capacity to follow a talk in English. The degree of English development is indicated by learner marks in English text. 80.6% strongly agree that the capacity to comprehend the English language Moreover, 59.7% accepted that the ability to express thoughts in English, 74.6% strongly agreed that the capacity to follow a talk in English, and 77.6% strongly agreed that the degree of English development is indicated by learner marks in English text.

The effect of use of literacy instruction on English language development in Private primary schools in Bugesera, Rwanda

The research established the relationship between uses of literacy instruction on English language development in Private primary schools in Bugesera, Rwanda.

The findings reveal that Results indicate the study found a strong relationship between students' understanding of English meaning and reading instruction, with a significant correlation between reading instruction and speaking instruction. The ability to grasp English language was positively related to food quality and quantity, with adjustments affecting promotion and completion rates. The capacity to convey thoughts in English was also significantly correlated with writing instruction, reading instruction, and speaking instruction.

Conclusions

Reconsidering the results from the present study discussed in chapter and the contrast made with past researches, the researcher elucidated concluding remarks per objectives: To the first objective and research question, the study concludes that the findings from the present research show that the The literacy instruction that affect English language development in Private primary schools are: Writing instruction, reading instruction, listening instruction and Speaking instruction.

Recommendations of the Study

Relying on the results gotten, the researcher provided the following: Partners in educational activities in the district under study should collaborate with the community for improving the level of speaking, reading, writing and listening English as a language of instruction.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bagambe, P. M. (2015). English Language Proficiency and Students' Performance in Secondary Schools in Rwanda: A Case Study of Bugesera District. African Scientific journal of research.
- [2] Bayerlein, L. (2020). The Impact of Prior Work-Experience on Student Learning Outcomes in. Journal of University Teaching & Learning Practice, 17(4), 2020. .
- [3] Butler, Y. G. (2018). What Level of English Proficiency Do Elementary School Teachers Need to Attain to Teach EFL? Case Studies from Korea, Taiwan, and Japan. onlinelibrary.
- [4] D'Angiulli, A. (2017). Literacy Instruction, SES, and Word-Reading Achievement in English-Language Learners and Children with English as a First Language: A Longitudinal Study. Journal of Research in Reading.
- [5] Jukes, M. C. (2017). Improving Literacy Instruction in Kenya Through Teacher Professional Development and Text Messages Support: A Cluster Randomized Trial. Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness.
- [6] Kumar, K. (2023). Language and Literacy Development of english language learners. national academies of science.
- [7] Linan-Thompson, S. (2019). Effectiveness of Supplemental Reading Instruction for Second-Grade English Language Learners with Reading Difficulties. University Press Chicago Journal. Récupéré sur <https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/abs/10.1086/499724>